

In vitro antimitotic activity and *in silico* study of some 6-fluoro-triazolo-benzothiazole analogues

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Received 21 July 2023 ♦ Accepted 2 August 2023 ♦ Published 28 September 2023

Citation: Podila N, Rudrapal M, Sibbala S, Bendale AR, Palakurthi Y, Babu MR, Manda K, Pecho RDC, Muddiseti S (2023) *In vitro* antimitotic activity and *in silico* study of some 6-fluoro-triazolo-benzothiazole analogues. Pharmacia 70(4): 887–894. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.70.e109898>

Abstract

In this work, nine 6-fluoro-triazolo-benzothiazole derivatives were prepared and evaluated for *in vitro* antimitotic activity. In addition, *in silico* study was also done using tubulin protein (PDB: 6QQN) by molecular docking method. Results revealed that TZ2 and TZ9 were the most active compounds with antimitotic action opposing the standard drug, aspirin. Results of molecular docking exhibited the inhibitory potential of triazolo-benzothiazole against tubulin protein. The mitotic study indicates the efficacy of triazolo-benzothiazole analogues in inhibiting the proliferation of cancer cells either by promoting microtubule formation or affecting microtubules, thereby preventing microtubule breakdown.

Keywords

Benzothiazole, 1,2,4-triazole, cancer, antimitotic activity, aspirin, mung beans

Introduction

Cancer is a major cause of mortality globally, in both industrialized and developing nations (Mollinedo and Gajate 2003). Many synthetic and natural anticancer medications cure various forms of leukaemias, lymphomas, and solid tumours. Despite great advances in cancer chemotherapy, the management of cancer is still a chal-

lenging task. Over the past decades, various highly active natural and synthetic compounds with anticancer potential have been discovered, including microtubule poisons such as paclitaxel and other taxanes, which have proved beneficial in treating certain cancers like breast cancer, lung cancer, and ovarian cancer.

Benzothiazole is an interesting moiety in medicinal chemistry that has been reported to exhibit anticancer, an-

titumor, antimicrobial, anticonvulsant, anti-diabetic, anti-tubercular, and antibacterial activity (Siddiqui et al. 2007; Rajeeva et al. 2009; Dewangan et al. 2010; Nitin et al. 2010; Naresh et al. 2013; Sharma et al. 2013; Prabhu et al. 2015; Naresh et al. 2021). The second position of the benzothiazole moiety is suitable for substitution. The benzothiazole moiety fused with triazole ring with halogen substitutions of the phenyl ring could be an ideal scaffold for the development of therapeutic agents against cancer and other infectious diseases (bacterial, fungal and tubercular). In this work, some novel 6-fluoro-triazolo-benzothiazole analogues were designed and synthesized for their evaluation as antimitotic agents (Fig. 1). To identify potential tubulin inhibitors *in silico* study of the designed analogues was also carried out by molecular docking method.

Figure 1. 6-fluoro-triazolo-benzothiazole scaffold.

Materials and methods

All the chemicals used were of synthetic grade. The melting point was determined by digital melting point apparatus. Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was used to monitor the progress of reaction progress by using GF₂₅₄ pre-coated aluminum plates (Merck), ethyl acetate: n-hexane (3:1) as the mobile phase, and ultra-violet (UV) chamber for visualization of spots. ELICIO FT-IR spectrometer was used to acquire the IR spectrum (Annavarapu et al. 2022). The ¹H-NMR spectra were recorded in deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO-d₆) using a BRUKER Av 400 spectrometer. Using Shimadzu GC-MS QP 5000, mass spectra (MS) were recorded.

Chemistry

Synthesis of 7-chloro-6-fluorobenzo[d]thiazol-2-amine

About 1.45 g (0.01 mole) of fluorochloro aniline and 8 gm (0.08 mole) of potassium thiocyanate were mixed with 20 mL of cold glacial acetic acid and 1.6 mL of bromine solution was added into it from a dropping funnel and agitated with a magnetic stirrer in an ice bath. The mixture

was agitated for 10 hours at room temperature after adding the bromine solution. Overnight, an orange precipitate was formed at the bottom of the flask, it was then added with 6 mL of water and the mixture was promptly heated to 85 °C and filtered. The reaction mixture was cooled and neutralized which finally yielded a dark brown precipitate. After benzene re-crystallization and animal charcoal treatment, 2-amino-6-fluoro-7-chloro-(1,3)-benzothiazole was obtained as green precipitate (1 gm, 51.02%, melted at 210–212 °C) after drying in 80 °C in an oven.

Synthesis of 7-chloro-6-fluoro-2-hydrazinylbenzo[d]thiazole

To a 500 mL round bottom flask, 10 mL of concentrated HCl was added drop wise to 12 mL (0.02 mole) of hydrazine hydrate while stirring at 5–10 °C. After cooling the solution, 20.2 gm of 7-chloro-6-fluoro 2-amino benzothiazole was added, followed by 60 mL of ethylene glycol. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 3 hours processed by first letting the residue sink to the bottom of a beaker filled with crushed ice, then filtering, drying, and recrystallizing with ethanol.

Synthesis of 8-chloro-7-fluoro-1,9a-dihydro[1,2,4] triazole [3,4-b][1,3] benzothiazole

About 2.19 gm of 7-chloro-6-fluoro-2-hydrazinyl-1,3-benzothiazole and 1 gm of potassium carbonate were added to 25 mL of formic acid in a 250 mL round bottom flask. The adduct was stabilized after two hours of refluxing in crushed ice. The residue was then purified and dried to obtain the pure product.

Synthesis of 8-chloro-7-fluoro-1-[4-methylphenyl]sulphonyl-1,9a-dihydro[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-b][1,3]benzothiazole

In a 500 mL of round bottom flask, 2.2 gm of 8-chloro-7-fluoro-1,9a-dihydro[1,2,4] triazole (0.013 mole) was transferred in the presence of pyridine and 1.71 g of *p*-toluene sulphonamide, (0.02 mole) after which it was refluxed for two hours, poured onto pulverized ice, drained, final purified residue was obtained by recrystallization with ethanol.

In a 100 mL round bottom flask, 2.7 gm of 8-chloro-7-fluoro-1-[4-methylphenyl]sulphonyl-1,9a-dihydro[1,2,4] triazole [3,4b] [1,3] benzothiazole was refluxed with equal quantities of primary and secondary aromatic amines for 2 hours in DMF. The mélange was chilled before being spread over pulverised ice. Using a sprinkle of activated charcoal, after alcohol and benzene separation, the material was filtered, dehydrated, and recrystallized from alcohol. The scheme of synthesis of 6-fluoro-triazolo-benzothiazole analogues is depicted in Fig. 2.

6-fluoro-3-[(4-methylphenyl) sulfonyl]-N-(2-amino phenylamino)-3,3a-dihydro[1,2,4] triazolo [5,1-b][1,3] benzothiazol-5-amine (TZ1): Yield: 83%; white powder; mp: 112–114 °C; mf: C₂₁H₁₈FN₅O₂S₂, mw: 455.52; R_f = 0.74 (EtOAc: n-But: CHCl₃ 2:1:1); FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1276.78, 1432.75, 1660, 1069, 1442, 1105, 1196; ¹H-NMR (DMSO-d₆, 300 MHz) δ ppm: 6.78–6.86 (m, 11H, Ar) 4.28 (s, 1H, NH₂) 3.01 (m, 3H, CH₃), 8.50 (s, 1H, NH); ¹³C-NMR (CDCl₃, 100

Figure 2. Scheme of synthesis for 6-fluoro-triazolo-benzothiazole analogues.

MHz) δ ppm: 24.3, 59.5, 104.8, 110.2, 113.5, 117.2, 119.1, 119.7, 119.9, 122.8, 127.2, 127.8, 129.2, 129.4, 129.8, 133.2, 136.7, 138.4, 141.5, 149.1, 154.8; MS (m/z), M^+ : 455.50.

*6-fluoro-3-[(4-methylphenyl)sulfonyl]-N-(4-hydroxypropanoic acid)-3,3a-dihydro [1,2,4] triazolo [5,1-*b*] [1,3] benzothiazol-5-amine (TZ2)*: Yield: 49%; Brown solid; mp: 118–122 °C; mf: $C_{24}H_{21}FN_4O_5S_2$; mw: 528.57; R_f = 0.69 (EtOAc: n-Bu: $CHCl_3$: 2:1:1); FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 1348.45, 1527.14, 1598.48, 1127.34, 1398.72, 1164.64, 1118.53; 1H -NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ ppm: 6.21–6.92 (m, 10H, Ar) 9.38 (s, 1H, NH), 1.96 (m, 3H, CH_3) 2.98 (s, 2H, CH_2), 9.81, 13.10 (d, 2H, OH); ^{13}C -NMR ($CDCl_3$, 100 MHz) δ ppm: 24.8, 35.5, 60.8, 65.9, 67.4, 82.7, 103.7, 104.8, 113.6, 114.8, 115.3, 128.1, 129.4, 129.6, 129.8, 132.2, 133.4, 133.8, 136.5, 141.4, 143.2, 154.0, 155.6, 174.2 MS (m/z), M^+ : 528.24.

*N-(carboxy phenyl amino)-6-fluoro-3-[(4-methyl phenyl) sulfonyl]-3,3a-dihydro [1,2,4] triazolo [5,1-*b*] [1,3] benzothiazol-5-amine (TZ3)*: Yield: 72.8%; orange solid; mp: 161–163 °C; mf: $C_{21}H_{17}FN_4O_3S_2$; mw: 456.41; R_f = 0.70 ($CHCl_3$: n-Bu: EtOAc: 1:2:1); FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 1298.21, 1521.57, 1614.57, 1152.86, 1487.45, 1019.26, 1224.26; 1H -NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ ppm: 7.16–7.23 (m, 8H, Ar), 9.38 (s, 1H, NH), 2.15 (m, 3H, CH_3) 2.99 (s, 2H,

CH_2), 9.87, 11.82 (d, 2H, OH), 3.14 (s, 1H, NH); ^{13}C -NMR ($CDCl_3$, 100 MHz) δ ppm: 24.6, 60.2, 104.2, 110.5, 113.4, 116.2, 116.8, 120.2, 120.6, 127.2, 127.6, 129.1, 129.4, 129.7, 133.3, 136.5, 141.6, 148.2, 149.1, 154.3, 162.6; MS (m/z), M^+ : 456.15.

*N-(4-methoxyphenylamino)-6-fluoro-3-[(4-methyl phenyl) sulfonyl]-3,3a-dihydro [1,2,4] triazolo [5,1-*b*] [1,3] benzothiazol-5-amine (TZ4)*: Yield: 48.6%; pink solid; mp: 186–188 °C; mf: $C_{22}H_{19}FN_4O_3S_2$; mw: 470.53; R_f = 0.53 ($CHCl_3$: n-But: EtOAc: 2:1:1); FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 1311.85, 1538.47, 1597.41, 1123.82, 1476.14, 1083.53, 1191.68; 1H -NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ ppm: 7.12–7.68 (m, 10H, Ar), 9.31 (s, 1H, NH), 3.01 (m, 3H, CH_3), 2.92 (s, 2H, CH_2), 3.27, 2.45 (s, 2H, CH_2); ^{13}C -NMR ($CDCl_3$, 100 MHz) δ ppm: 24.2, 55.9, 60.4, 104.8, 110.3, 113.6, 115.2, 115.6, 120.1, 120.8, 127.2, 127.4, 129.3, 129.6, 129.9, 131.9, 133.6, 141.6, 149.5, 150.2, 152.4, 154.6; MS (m/z), M^+ : 470.25.

*6-fluoro-3-[(4-methylphenyl)sulfonyl]-morpho-nyl-3,3a-dihydro [1,2,4] triazolo [5,1-*b*] [1,3] benzothiazol-5-amine (TZ5)*: Yield: 63.14%, milkfish; mp: 168–172 °C; mf: $C_{19}H_{20}FN_5O_3S_2$; mw: 449.51; R_f = 0.82 (EtOAc:n-Bu: $CHCl_3$: 2:1:1); FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 1198.57, 1457.01, 1668.27, 1125.65, 1502.48, 1183.34, 1210.01; 1H -NMR (DMSO- d_6 ,

300 MHz) δ ppm: 7.15–7.83 (m, 5H, Ar), 1.98 (m, 3H, CH₃) 3.18 (s, 2H, CH₂), 3.01–3.47 (m, 4H, CH₂); ¹³C-NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) δ ppm: 24.6, 41.7, 56.1, 56.3, 60.4, 64.2, 64.5, 104.5, 105.7, 113.4, 127.2, 127.7, 128.4, 129.4, 129.9, 132.6, 136.6, 141.8, 143.2; MS (m/z), M⁺: 449.32.

6-fluoro-(4-pyrrolidinyl)-3-[(4-methylphenyl)sulphonyl]-3,3a-dihydro [1,2,4]triazolo [5,1-b] [1,3] benzothiazol-5-amine (TZ6): Yield: 51.5%; cream; mp: 176–178 °C; mf: C₁₉H₁₉FN₄O₂S₂; mw: 418.50; R_f = 0.87 (EtOAc: n-But:CHCl₃ 2:1:1); FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1301.20, 1558.51, 1637.68, 1084.45, 1493.29, 1137.87, 1204.60; ¹H-NMR (DMSO-d₆, 300 MHz) δ ppm: 6.78–6.85 (m, 6H, Ar), 3.00 (m, 3H, CH₃) 1.99 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.96–3.47 (m, 4H, CH₂); ¹³C-NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) δ ppm: 24.6, 25.2, 25.5, 51.2, 51.8, 60.4, 104.7, 104.8, 105.4, 112.3, 126.3, 126.9, 127.8, 129.3, 129.8, 132.5, 136.2, 140.5, 142.4; MS (m/z), M⁺: 418.27.

6-fluoro-N-diethylamino-3-[(4-methylphenyl)sulphonyl]-3,3a-dihydro [1,2,4] triazolo [5,1-b] [1,3] benzothiazol-5-amine (TZ7): Yield: 63.7%; blue; mp: 110–112 °C; mf: C₁₉H₂₁FN₄O₂S₂; mw: 420.52; R_f = 0.52 (EtOAc : n-But: CHCl₃ 2:1:1); FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1310.21, 1522.57, 1685.01, 1107.27, 1524.84, 1098.21, 1267.47; ¹H-NMR (DMSO-d₆, 300 MHz) δ ppm: 7.04–7.34 (m, 5H, Ar), 2.04–3.64 (m, 6H, CH₃) 2.97 (m, 4H, CH₂); ¹³C-NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) δ ppm: 24.15, 43.1, 52.3, 54.8, 61.2, 64.8, 64.9, 101.3, 104.3, 112.6, 123.4, 127.4, 128.3, 128.7, 129.4, 131.2, 133.8, 141.8, 144.9; MS (m/z), M⁺: 420.12.

1-[6-fluoro-7-(4-phenethyl amino)-3-[4-methyl phenyl] sulphonyl]-3,3a dihydro [1, 2, 4] triazole [5,1-b] [1,3] benzothiazole (TZ8): Yield: 57.9%; green; mp: 116–119 °C; mf: C₂₃H₂₁FN₄O₂S₂; mw: 468.56; R_f = 0.72 (EtOAc: n-But: CHCl₃: 2:1:1); FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1317.34, 1503.04, 1621.27, 1089.57, 1457.14, 1200.62, 1243.18; ¹H-NMR (DMSO-d₆, 300 MHz) δ ppm: 7.07–7.64 (m, 11H, Ar), 3.05–3.83 (m, 4H, CH₂) 7.68 (s, H, NH) 3.08

(m, 3H, CH₃); ¹³C-NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) δ ppm: 23.4, 25.3, 44.8, 53.6, 60.8, 62.7, 69.4, 103.5, 106.7, 110.2, 114.6, 124.6, 127.6, 128.9, 129.1, 129.6, 129.8, 130.4, 132.7, 134.8, 1412.3, 144.6, 148.3; MS (m/z), M⁺: 468.25.

6-fluoro-3-[(4-methyl phenyl) sulphonyl]-5-(naphthyl amino)-3,3a-dihydro[1,2,4] triazolo [5,1- b] [1,3] Benzothiazole (TZ9): Yield:63.78%; violet; mp: 155–158 °C; mf: C₂₅H₁₉FN₄O₂S₂; mw: 490.57; R_f = 0.91 (EtOAc: n-Bul:CHCl₃: 2:1:1); FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1314.47, 1582.17, 1605.23, 1041.89, 1487.24, 1317.27, 1151.07; ¹H-NMR (DMSO-d₆, 300 MHz) δ ppm: 7.13–7.82 (m, 6H, aromatic), 3.14–3.57 (m, 4H, CH₂) 9.27 (s, 4H, NH) 2.37 (m, 3H, CH₃); ¹³C-NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) δ ppm: 21.3, 23.5, 26.4, 27.6, 40.6, 45.7, 61.2, 64.3, 84.5, 102.3, 108.4, 110.8, 116.2, 125.3, 126.4, 126.8, 128.6, 128.9, 129.5, 130.2, 130.6, 130.9, 131.2, 133.4, 1491.57; MS (m/z), M⁺: 490.30.

Evaluation of antimitotic activity

The antimitotic activity was evaluated according to a previously reported method (Raheel et al. 2017). For six hours, the average weight of mung beans was steeped in the standard, control, and test solutions. The solution was drained after six hours and the radical, which is 1.0–1.5 cm long was measured. Mass, radical length and seed germination were recorded.

Molecular docking

Molecular docking was performed on PyRx 0.8 platform (Ghosh et al. 2021; Junejo et al. 2021; James et al. 2022; Archana et al. 2023; Celik et al. 2023; Devasia et al. 2023). PyRx determines ligand-protein binding affinity in molecular docking (Rudrapal et al. 2022a; Rudrapal et al. 2022b; Rudrapal et al. 2022c; Rudrapal et al. 2022d; Rudrapal et al. 2022e; Zothantluanga et al. 2022; Rudra-

Table 1. Antimitotic data of synthesized compounds.

Sl. No.	Compound code	Name of drug and concentration	Initial weight (gms)	Weight at		Drain radical length		No. of seeds germinated		% seeds germinated	
				T ₀ (gm)	T ₄₈ (gm)	T ₀ (cm)	T ₄₈ (cm)	T ₀	T ₄₈	T ₀	T ₄₈
1	TZ1	1 mg	1.52	2.63	3.89	1.29	1.38	9	11	50%	60%
		3 mg	1.54	3.17	4.21	1.19	1.30	12	14	55%	65%
2.	TZ2	1 mg	1.56	3.21	4.52	1.12	1.25	11	12	50%	65%
		3 mg	1.54	3.52	4.12	0.81	1.06	12	13	55%	60%
3.	TZ3	1 mg	1.52	3.12	4.21	1.00	1.12	7	9	35%	45%
		3 mg	1.54	2.25	3.74	0.89	1.21	9	11	40%	45%
4.	TZ4	1 mg	1.54	3.09	3.99	0.78	0.84	9	11	50%	60%
		3 mg	1.55	3.13	3.89	0.52	0.72	10	12	55%	65%
5.	TZ5	1 mg	1.55	3.48	3.85	0.69	0.89	9	10	50%	65%
		3 mg	1.56	3.24	3.98	0.71	0.74	10	11	55%	60%
6.	TZ6	1 mg	1.54	2.48	3.61	0.72	0.79	9	10	50%	55%
		3 mg	1.52	3.04	3.94	0.74	0.82	10	11	40%	55%
7.	TZ7	1 mg	1.55	3.34	4.18	0.89	1.14	9	10	40%	50%
		3 mg	1.54	3.42	3.99	0.86	0.83	10	11	40%	55%
8.	TZ8	1 mg	1.52	3.45	3.75	0.89	0.86	8	10	45%	55%
		3 mg	1.55	3.51	3.81	0.85	0.94	9	11	40%	55%
9.	TZ9	1 mg	1.52	2.73	3.93	1.32	1.45	10	12	50%	60%
		3 mg	1.54	3.07	4.02	1.25	1.32	11	13	55%	65%
10.	Standard Aspirin	1 mg	1.56	3.64	4.32	0.52	0.58	7	9	35%	45%
		3 mg	1.54	3.42	4.12	0.58	0.62	6	8	30%	40%
11.	Control		1.56	3.52	4.32	1.05	0.98	9	11	45%	55%

pal et al. 2023). Tubulin protein (PDB: 6QQN) was used at a resolution of 1.50 Å. The size of grid box was 0.3750 Å. The 200 step MMFF94 force field with an RMS gradient of 0.1 was used for the study. The protein's binding site (grid box) was chosen first to perform docking (Othman et al. 2021; Kumar et al. 2022; Kumar et al. 2023; Pasala et al. 2022a; Pasala et al. 2022b; Rashid et al. 2022; Issahaku et al. 2023; Paul et al. 2023). All synthesized ligands were docked in the active site of the protein molecule. The PyRx score classified all ligands by binding affinity. The ligands were categorized by their binding energies.

Results and discussion

Chemistry

Fig. 2 shows the synthetic strategy of 6-fluoro triazolo-benzothiazole derivatives (TZ1–TZ9). The final compounds are derivatives of 8-chloro-7-fluoro-1-[4-methylphenyl]sulphonyl-1,9a-dihydro[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-b][1,3]benzothiazole. As presented in the experimental section, FT-IR, ¹H-NMR, and MS data supported the structure of synthesized compounds.

Antimitotic activity

Anti-mitotic activity was tested for all the compounds (TZ1–TZ9) (Table 1). Aspirin was used as standard compound at 1 and 3 mg/mL. Results revealed that TZ2 and TZ9 were the most active opposing the standard drug. TZ1, TZ7, and TZ4 also exhibited appreciable activity. *In vitro* anticancer drug screening requires antimitotic action. In the present study, the mitotic index of 6-fluoro triazolo-benzothiazole analogues indicates the efficacy of compounds in inhibiting the proliferation of cancer cells either by promoting microtubule formation or affecting microtubules, thereby preventing microtubule breakdown. This causes the cells to become so congested with microtubules that they can no longer divide and develop. As a result, cells stop dividing and eventually perish via apoptosis.

Docking assessment

The three-dimensional structure of tubulin and guanosine triphosphate (PDB: 6QQN) was used in the study. Prior to docking active site amino acid residues were identified. The following amino acids viz., Gln146, Thr145, Gln11, Ser178, Ala180, Asn101, Asp98, Glu71, Ser140, Gln144, Gln143, Ala100, ASP69, Tyr224, Ser140, and Ala99 are present in the catalytic pocket of the protein molecule, as shown in Fig. 3. Ramachandran map verified the protein, as represented in Fig. 4.

PyRx calculated binding energies of protein-ligand complexes. The protein-ligand interaction is a measure of binding affinity. The binding affinity of TZ9 (-10.9 kcal/mol) was the highest among the selected molecules whose binding energy was greater than that of standard aspirin

Figure 3. Amino acids present in the active site of the catalytic pocket of the tubulin receptor (PDB id: 6QQN).

Figure 4. Ramachandran plot of tubulin receptor (PDB id: 6QQN).

(-6.5 kcal/mol) and co-crystal ligand (guanosine triphosphate) (-8.2 kcal/mol). Table 2 presents two dimensional (2D) interactions between ligands (TZ1–TZ9) and 6QQN. Fig. 5a–d displays two dimensional (2D) interactions between TZ2 and 6QQN, TZ9 with 6QQN, aspirin and 6QQN, and guanosine triphosphate with 6QQN.

Conclusion

In this work, nine 6-fluoro-triazolo-benzothiazole derivatives were prepared and evaluated for *in vitro* antimitotic activity. In addition, *in silico* study was also done using tubulin protein (PDB: 6QQN) by molecular docking method. The antimitotic study indicates the efficacy of triazolo-benzothiazole analogues in inhibiting the proliferation of cancer cells either by promoting microtubule formation or affecting microtubules, thereby preventing microtubule breakdown.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Table 2. Compounds and their binding energies.

Sl. No.	Compound code	Binding energy (kcal/mole)	No. of hydrogen bonds	Ligand group	Interacting amino acid residue
1	TZ1	-9.7	4		Ser178, Gln77, Ser140, Gln11
2	TZ2	-9.8	4		Asp69, Gln11, Ser140, Ser178
3	TZ3	-8.7	3		Tyr224, Glu22, Ala19
4	TZ4	-8.3	3		Ser140, Tyr224, Ser178
5	TZ5	-8.5	2		Val177, Ser140
6	TZ6	-8.7	1		Ser140
7	TZ7	-7.9	2		Arg229, Gln15
8	TZ8	-8.4	3		Thr82, Glu77, Gln15
9	TZ9	-10.1	4		Ala12, Gln11, Ser140, Asn101
10	Aspirin	-6.5	1		Asn206

Figure 5. (a) 2D interaction of TZ2 on 6QQN, (b) 2D interaction of TZ9 on 6QQN, (c) 2D interaction of aspirin on 6QQN, and (d) 2D interaction of guanosine triphosphate on 6QQN.

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